

scRNA-seq_analysis_scripts.zip

File name	Description
01_preprocessing_demultiplexing_template.Rmd	Process CellRanger outputs and generate individual Seurat objects, including demultiplexing
02_integration.Rmd	Integrate the single-cell objects
03_scanpy_plot.ipynb	Generate manuscript plots in Scanpy
04_processing_for_DESeq2.Rmd	Prepare DESeq2 objects for differential-expression and pathway analysis
05_DESeq2_DEG.Rmd	Differential gene-expression analysis
06.1_pre_requested_Matrix.utils.R	Utility script for required packages and helper functions
06.2_GSEA.Rmd	Gene set enrichment analysis
07.GSVA.Rmd	GSVA pathway activity analysis
08.velocityto.ipynb	RNA velocity / trajectory analysis
09.expression_distence.ipynb	Transcriptomic distance analysis
10.CellChat_comparision.Rmd	Cell-cell communication analysis

Data files from Zenodo

Directory or file	Description	figure(s)
immunofluourscance-image-spatial-analysis_ERE_or_ERa-positive-macrophages_distribution.zip	Spatial analysis measuring ERA+ / ERE+ macrophage distance to nearest tumor cells	Fig S4G-L
immunofluourscance-image-spatial-analysis_diffusion-lesions_niche-labeling-model-comparisions.zip	Spatial analysis comparing niche-labeling methods in bone metastasis diffusion lesions	Fig 2E, Fig S2B, Fig S2C
immunofluourscance_image_spatial_analysis_demostration_scripts_and_data.zip	Demonstration scripts and data for customized spatial analysis	/
immunofluourscance-image-spatial-analysis_isolate-lesions_niche-labeling-model-comparisions.zip	Spatial analysis comparing niche-labeling methods in isolated lesions	Fig 2D, Fig S2A
immunofluourscance-image-spatial-analysis_T_cell_distribution_in_ctrl-Esr1KO.zip	Spatial analysis measuring T cell distribution in the tumor microenvironment	Fig 7
SAMENT_single_cell_per-sample-Seurat_objects.zip	Individual SAMENT Seurat and Scanpy objects from demultiplexed scRNA-seq, without cell-type annotation	/
SAMENT_single_cell_integrated_objects.zip	Integrated SAMENT Seurat and Scanpy objects, batch-corrected and cell-type annotated	All SAMENT scRNA-seq related panels
cellranger_demultiplexed_scRNA-seq_matrix.zip	Cell Ranger scRNA-seq outputs	/
Macrophage_LysM_Esr1_KO_single_cell_integrated_objects.zip	Integrated LysM-Esr1 Seurat and Scanpy objects, batch-corrected and cell-type annotated	All LysM-Esr1 scRNA-seq related panels
Macrophage_LysM_Esr1_KO_single_cell_per-sample-Seurat_objects.zip	Individual LysM-Esr1 Seurat and Scanpy objects from demultiplexed scRNA-seq, without cell-type annotation	/
scRNA-seq_analysis_scripts.zip	All scRNA-seq analysis scripts	/